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Research Article

THE ROLE OF CT UROGRAPHY IN CASE OF HAEMATURIA

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Abstract:

Introduction: Haematuria is one of the most common presentations of urinary tract pathologies and always warrants serious concern, both to the patient as well as the treating physician. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the main role of CT urography in case of haematuria. **Material and methods:** This prospective study was conducted in Lahore medical and dental college Lahore during 2021 to 2022. The data was collected from 50 patients of haematuria from the OPD of the hospital. The patients was undergo CECT examination after obtaining detailed clinical history. Patient is advised to be nil by mouth six hours before the study. **Results:** The data was collected from 50 patients. There were 38 females and 12 males. The most common cause of obstructive uropathy was stone disease i.e. renal, ureteric or both and 75.0% patients in group A and 65.0% in group B, presented with it followed by other causes i.e. carcinomas, pyonephrosis and PUJ obstruction as shown in table 01. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that multi-detector CT urography detects the entire spectrum of urinary tract pathologies causing haematuria with high accuracy.

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INTRODUCTION:

Haematuria is one of the most common presentations of urinary tract pathologies and always warrants serious concern, both to the patient as well as the treating physician. Haematuria is one of the most common manifestations of urinary tract pathologies like calculi, neoplasm, infection, trauma, medications, coagulopathy, developmental anomalies and renal parenchymal diseases and always warrants serious concern¹. Until the beginning of the 21st century, intravenous urography (IVU) was the initial method for genitourinary imaging. But now a days MDCT urography is emerging as imaging modality of choice².

MDCT urography is dened as multidetector CT examination of the kidneys, ureters and bladder with at least one imaging series acquired during the excretory-phase following. intravenous contrast administration CT urography is rapidly becoming accepted as the preferred test for diagnosing urinary tract disease responsible for haematuria because of superior spatial resolution, higher speed, isotropic reconstruction capability, excellent 3D multiplanar reformats and depiction of entire urinary tract in single breath hold examination CT urography combines the benefits of excretory urography with those of cross sectional imaging into a single study which depicts the renal parenchyma, collecting system, ureters and bladder³.

CT (Computed Tomography) Urography is a diagnostic examination which is optimized for imaging the kidneys, ureters and bladder with thin slice MDCT (Multi detector computed tomography), intravenous administration of contrast medium and image acquisition in the excretory phase⁴. CT Urography facilitates multiplanar imaging of the urinary system, thus is an excellent technique in evaluating the urinary tract calculi and renal masses with high sensitivity and specificity. CT Urography is essentially defined as a CT examination of the urinary tract which includes non-contrast or unenhanced phase imaging and imaging after administration of contrast⁵. According to The European Society of Urogenital Radiology CT Urography is a diagnostic examination which is optimized for imaging the kidneys, ureters and bladder with thin slice MDCT, intravenous administration of contrast medium and image acquisition in the excretory phase. The non-contrast or unenhanced images are useful for evaluation of fat-containing lesions, calculi and parenchymal calcifications and also to provide baseline attenuation for assessment of lesion enhancement⁶.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the main role of CT urography in case of haematuria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Table 01: Causes of Obstructive Uropathy

<i>Causes</i>	<i>No. of patients</i>	<i>%age</i>
<i>Stone disease</i>	75	75.0
• Renal	40	40.0
• Ureteric	25	25.0
• Renal + Ureteric	10	10.0
<i>Carcinomas</i>	20	20.0
• Urinary Bladder	03	3.0
• Prostate	02	2.0
• Cervix	05	5.0
• Others	10	10.0
Pyonephrosis	03	3.0
PUJ Obstruction	02	2.0

Table 02: Primary cause of ureteral obstruction.

	Ureteral stent	Percutaneous nephrostomy
Benign causes	40	16
Malignancy	26	28
Cervical cancer	19	9
Prostate cancer	4	5
Colon cancer	1	7
Bladder cancer	2	1
Stomach cancer	0	1

This prospective study was conducted in Lahore medical and dental college Lahore during 2021 to 2022. The data was collected from 50 patients of haematuria from the OPD of the hospital. The patients were undergoing CECT examination after obtaining detailed clinical history. Patient is advised to be nil by mouth six hours before the study. First phase is the non-contrast phase and second phase is the corticomedullary phase, which was acquired following a delay of 25-80 seconds after administration of 100 ml (2.5ml/sec) of intravenous non-ionic low osmolar contrast medium to differentiate normal variants of renal parenchyma from renal masses and better depiction of tumor hypervascularity. CT scan performed with a Multi detector row CT scanner and CT scans was obtained from the diaphragm to the bladder. The follow up diagnosis will be established on the basis of histopathologic findings. The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 50 patients. There were 38 females and 12 males. The most common cause of obstructive uropathy was stone disease i.e. renal, ureteric or both and 75.0% patients in group A and 65.0% in group B, presented with it followed by other causes i.e. carcinomas, pyonephrosis and PUJ obstruction as shown in table 01.

Ovarian cancer	0	1
Lung cancer	0	1
Endometrial cancer	0	1
Lymphoma	0	1
Breast cancer	0	1

Extensive ureteral injury was the most common cause requiring urinary diversion among the benign etiologies; cervical cancer was the most common malignancy associated with ureteral obstructions. The two retrospective reviewers identified 24 of the 27 neoplastic foci on MDCT urography, including all 18 urothelial tumors that were identified prospectively and six additional lesions. These six lesions were found in six patients. In four patients, a second focus of malignancy missed during the prospective review was found during the retrospective review. The six foci that were not seen prospectively but were seen in retrospect consisted of three small masses in the intrarenal collecting system. **Figure 1:** CT scan shows upper pole infundibular urothelial wall thickening.

DISCUSSION:

Early and accurate diagnosis of etiological factor helps in early and effective management. Conventional diagnostic test like IVU is complicated, long and less sensitive and specific compared to MDCT urography for detection of small tumor and calculi. Although ultrasound is very effective in detecting renal cystic lesions, this modality also has poor sensitivity for detecting solid renal lesions less than 3 cm⁷.

MRI has been recently used to evaluate the urinary system. However, the inability of MRI to pick up calcination is an inherent drawback of this modality in its utility in diagnosing urinary pathologies⁸. Also the cost and lack of easy availability restricts its use. At present the use of MR urography is limited to children, pregnant women, in renal insufficiency and in 8 patients with contrast allergy⁹. The ability of CT urography to evaluate the renal parenchyma as well as the urothelium in a single investigation has prompted

many authors to moot it as a potential one stop investigation for the 1 spectrum of urinary tract disorder with haematuria¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that multidetector CT urography detects the entire spectrum of urinary tract pathologies causing haematuria with high accuracy. CT Urography is a precise examination for the evaluation of urinary tract pathologies.

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